

THE GUTTA-VISIR SYSTEM FOR OPERATIONAL CO₂ EMISSION SAVINGS FROM FERRIES

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SUMMARY

GUTTA-VISIR is a service for operationally providing least-CO₂ ferry routes. It combines numerical meteorological forecasts with both the ship route optimisation model VISIR and a dedicated environment for operational production. The regions of interest are the Adriatic and Northern Ionian Seas. The optimal routes are computed at the CMCC high-performance computing facility by means of the VISIR model and then made available through a dedicated web application (www.gutta-visir.eu). Both the CO₂ and the Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) savings resulting from route optimisation are provided to the end users. GUTTA-VISIR has been in continuous operation since November 2021 and 39,600 among the routes published since were statistically assessed.

It is found that the maximum CO₂ savings for a given route are related to the average sea state, that the CO₂ savings on any given route are nearly exponentially distributed, and that the largest mean savings are obtained for routes in the southern part of the basin. While the average savings for these short-sea routes in a relatively calm basin are around one percent, two-digit savings relative CO₂ emissions can be obtained on specific dates and routes. Furthermore, it is seen that the route optimisation process can account for about one tenth of the CII reductions required in 2023 by the International Maritime Organization.

These results provide a first objective assessment of the potential of ship routing for decarbonisation of short-sea shipping.

NOMENCLATURE

α	angle of attack of waves (relative true angle between waves and course)
CII	carbon intensity indicator (various units)
CMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CO ₂	carbon dioxide emissions (t)
χ	engine fractional load (%)
$-\Delta\text{CO}_2$	CO ₂ relative savings (with respect to the geodetic route, %)
EEA	European Economic Area
GHG	greenhouse gas(es)
GT	gross tonne
GUTTA	savinG fUel and emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region
HPC	high performance computing
H_s	significant wave height (m)
SOG	speed over ground (kts)
STW	speed through water (kts)
VISIR	discoVerIng Safe and efflcient Routes
w	surface ocean current intensity (kts)

1. INTRODUCTION

We live at the time of a climate crisis. The United Nations (UN) through several agencies have reviewed the scientific foundations (IPCC), the impacts (WMO, UNEP), and the policy instruments (UNFCCC) to address such a crisis. The general understanding is that humanity is lagging in taking action to remove the cause of this crisis. Namely: a deep alteration of the global carbon cycle, due to the direct emission of large amounts of greenhouse gases (GHG) through combustion of fossil fuels and cement production, as well as to the reduction of the GHG removal processes from the atmosphere, due to changes in land use, land cover, and forestry [5]. The resulting enhancement of the natural greenhouse effect has led to global warming, with consequences in terms of environmental degradation, natural disasters, weather extremes, food and water insecurity, economic disruption, conflicts, and climate migrations. To change course, together with nature-based solutions, support to scalable decarbonisation technologies was recently emphasised by the UN¹. This must hold for the sector of shipping too. Shipping as such was not explicitly included in the resolutions of the Paris

¹ <https://www.un.org/en/un75/climate-crisis-race-we-can-win>

Agreement². However, the UN pushed the maritime sector to deliver a strategy for contributing to decarbonisation. This was agreed upon by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) in 2018 [6].

IMO also approved the first concrete measures to be applied in the short term. Specific metrics, called Carbon Intensity Indicators (CII) have been introduced. CIIs all take the form of a CO₂ amount divided by some representation of transport work. The baseline for the mandated CII reduction is the year 2019, and the reduction rates increase every year till 2026. Subsequent reductions have still to be agreed upon³. While several Member States noted that the IMO Initial Strategy will be insufficient to deliver a contribution in line with the Paris Agreement, a revision of the IMO initial strategy is due by 2023 and should enter in force by 2027 [7].

In the meantime, the European Union (EU) has made independent steps to accelerate maritime decarbonisation. The CO₂ emission data of all vessels above 5,000 GT calling at EEA harbours have been published since 2018 [11]. This database shall be used for determining the allowances due by the ship companies, once the sector will be part of the EU-Emissions Trading System. This was proposed in the frame of the fitfor55 legislative package⁴. At the current price⁵ and CO₂ emission level, the total value of allowances for shipping in the EEA can be estimated to be in the order of ten billion Euro per year. During the last UNFCCC conference in Glasgow, several UN Member States agreed to establish at least six green corridors by the middle of this decade (“Clydebank declaration” at COP26⁶). Fully decarbonised fuels or propulsion technologies should be available at ports of a green corridor.

All these measures and proposals will necessarily make shipping more expensive than today. Thus, saving both fuel consumption and GHG emissions will be increasingly important. This is one of the reasons why voyage optimization or ship routing can play a role in facilitating both the energy transition and the economic viability of a low-carbon shipping industry. Furthermore, voyage optimization can apply to both newbuilds and retrofits of existing vessels. However, it is often difficult to estimate to what extent it could impact a decarbonisation pathway. Indeed, academic literature usually focuses on case studies, while data from commercial routing systems are not available for assessment. To close this knowledge gap, open access to the source code of a routing model would be extremely beneficial. However, to go beyond the level of a case study, a model should be operationally executed.

This is exactly where this paper would like to contribute. CMCC has been developing the VISIR open-source model⁷ for weather routing for the past ten years. During the Italy-Croatia Interreg project GUTTA⁸ the VISIR model was further developed and used for operational production of least-CO₂ routes for ferries in the Adriatic Sea. This basin connects Italy to Slovenia, Croatia, Montenegro, Albania, and Greece. Its maximum width of about 110 nautical miles in direction normal to its elongation axis makes overnight ferry crossings possible. Therefore, the scientific and practical question arises, if even short sea shipping could appreciably benefit from ship route optimization. This question can be answered through the GUTTA-VISIR operational service. It has been operational for about one year now, and the data produced were systematically assessed, as documented in the remainder of this paper.

In Sect.2 the materials and methods used, i.e. the VISIR model (Sect.2.1) and the GUTTA-VISIR system (Sect.2.2) are presented. The results, in Sect.3, are subdivided into a short review of the GUTTA-VISIR web application (Sect.3.1) and an analysis of data collected, with respect to both the CO₂ and CII savings (Sect.3.2). Our conclusions are drawn in Sect.4.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section presents the key materials and methods developed for producing the results given later in Sect.3. The materials and methods consist of the VISIR-2 ship routing model, documented in Sect.2.1, and the GUTTA-VISIR operational service, described in Sect.2.2.

2.1 THE VISIR-2 SHIP ROUTING MODEL

VISIR-2 is a python software meant for computing optimal ship routes in presence of dynamic marine weather fields. It was documented in [8]. VISIR-2 was inspired and validated vs. its predecessor; the matlab-coded VISIR-1 model [9]. The main model components of VISIR-2 are a vessel response model, a processor of environmental fields, a path planning component, and a suite of visualisation routines. They are briefly reviewed in the subsequent paragraphs.

² <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/the-paris-agreement>

³ <https://www.dnv.com/news/imo-update-marine-environment-protection-committee-mepc-76-203128>

⁴ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/european-green-deal/delivering-european-green-deal/increasing-ambition-eu-emissions-trading_en

⁵ <https://tradingeconomics.com/commodity/carbon>

⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/cop-26-clydebank-declaration-for-green-shipping-corridors/cop-26-clydebank-declaration-for-green-shipping-corridors>

⁷ www.visir-model.net

⁸ <https://bit.ly/guttaproject>

2.1 (a) Vessel response model

The vessel speed through water (STW) of a ferry was estimated from the outcome of a ship simulator installed at the University of Zadar (a Partner in the Italy-Croatia GUTTA project which also funded the development of GUTTA-VISIR). The hardware consisted of the Wärtsilä-Transas Marine NTPro 5000 Navigation Simulator coupled to the Wärtsilä ERS-LCHS 5000 TechSim engine-room simulator. The vessel was a Ro-Pax ferry with a twin, four-stroke engine (MAN Diesel 32/40 Twin Medium Speed) with controllable pitch propeller. Some vessel characteristics are provided in Tab.1. while for more technical details the reader can refer to [13].

Table 1: Parameters of the modelled ferry.

Name	Symbol	Value	Units
Length at waterline	Lwl	114	m
Hull coefficient	Cb	0.54	-
Deadweight	DWT	4,050	t
Gross tonnage	GT	14,000	t
Main engine power	Pme	4,000	kW
Main engine rated speed	n	750	rpm
Service speed	Vs	19	kts

The simulator was operated in the absence of sea currents, as they were added later as described in Sect. 2.1.c. Regular waves of significant height H_s and with a wave dispersion typical for the central Adriatic Sea were then generated, with variable angles of attack α with respect to the ferry. The engine load factor χ varied between 70 and 100%. The STW was a direct output of the simulator, while the CO₂ emission rate was estimated from the product of the specific fuel consumption and the power delivered at the propeller shaft, times a convenient emission factor for the actual fuel type used. The multi-dimensional response of the ferry (as a function of H_s , χ , and α) was published and commented on in [8].

2.1 (b) Environmental fields

As VISIR-2 is a graph-based model [8], it was necessary to define the graph edge weights to be later used by the path planner (Sect.2.1.c). To this end, the environmental fields from data-assimilative ocean models must be represented on graph edges. Also, for correctly capturing the field dynamics, they are sampled at a time resolution higher than in the original numerical products. This requires an interpolation, both in space and time. For the present application, forecast fields from the Copernicus Marine Service⁹ (CMS) are used,

- The MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_WAV_006_017 sea state product (VHM0, VMDR variables),
- The MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013 sea circulation product (uo, vo variables).

They both have a spatial resolution of 1/24 degree (2.5 miles in the meridional direction) and an hourly resolution (hourly instantaneous fields for waves, hourly mean values for currents). These products are computed from numerical models making use of data assimilation. Satellite sea wave height data are assimilated for the former and sea level, temperature-salinity profiles, sea surface temperature for the latter. The graph grid where the fields were remapped had a resolution of 1/12 degree, while the temporal resolution was 30 minutes. §

2.1 (c) Path planning component

The vessel's speed over ground (SOG) is formed from vector composition of the STW and the sea surface current velocity [9]. The STW is obtained from the vessel response (Sect.2.1.a) in correspondence of the actual significant wave height and direction from the dynamic environmental fields (Sect.2.1.b). Then, the SOG is used to compute the time for sailing across any graph edge, at each point in time. A path finding algorithm makes use of this information to extract the optimal routes. The algorithm used in VISIR-2 belongs to the family of graph-search methods [3]. Specifically, it is a modified version of the time-honoured Dijkstra's algorithm [4]. The algorithm was first generalised to deal with dynamic edge weights, proving its outcome vs. a semi-analytical benchmark [9]. Then, it was extended to also compute least-CO₂ paths

⁹ <https://marine.copernicus.eu/>

[8]. As a matter of fact, three variants of this algorithm are now available in VISIR-2: a static one, to compute least-distance routes making use of just bathymetry and shoreline as constraints; two dynamic ones, to compute least-time and least-CO₂ routes.

2.1 (d) Visualisation

A typical graphical output from VISIR-2 is shown in Fig.1. It includes both optimal routes and environmental fields. The departure location is always portrayed as a star. The three optimal routes are displayed with different colours. The fields are displayed in grey tones. To provide dynamic information via a static picture, the fields are rendered with concentric shells originating at the departure location. The shape of these shells is defined by isochrones. These are lines joining all sea locations which can be reached from the origin upon sailing for a given amount of time. This way, at any route waypoint, the field (either significant wave height H_s or current magnitude w) is portrayed at the time the vessel is supposed to be at that location.

Figure 1: Optimal routes (blue/red/green, solid lines for distance/time/CO₂ respectively) and isochrones (golden, dashed lines) on top the significant wave height field (shaded grey tones). Between each pair of isochrones, the field is displayed with hourly resolution. CO₂ and CII savings of the green with respect to the blue route are given in the top right.

2.2 THE GUTTA-VISIR OPERATIONAL SERVICE

The GUTTA-VISIR¹⁰ system was conceived to operationally compute and publish optimal ferry routes, based on marine forecasts. The service was developed in the frame of the Italy-Croatia Interreg project GUTTA¹¹ and was powered by the VISIR-2 model. Through an operational chain on a high-performance computing (HPC) facility and a dedicated web-application, GUTTA-VISIR daily provides an end-user with both graphical and numerical products. The access to the service is open and free. Fig.2 provides an overview of the system. The data flow originates at the daily (or bi-daily for waves) feed of CMS products for the Mediterranean Sea and ends on the user's device. Its back- and frontend components are shortly described in the following two paragraphs.

¹⁰ www.gutta-visir.eu

¹¹ <https://bit.ly/guttaproject>

Figure 2: Overall architecture of GUTTA-VISIR. The upper row contains the name of the data streams, the intermediate one the software components, and the bottom one the hosting devices. The columns depict chronologically ordered processes. The logos next to the boxes refer to the programming languages they are coded in.

2.2 (a) Backend

The backend component is the operational chain routinely executed at the CMCC HPC facility, to produce all numerical and some of the graphical outputs of GUTTA-VISIR.

The HPC is based on a supercomputer (“zeus”¹²) with 348 SD530 Lenovo bi-processor nodes (for a total of 12,528 cores) all interconnected by means of an Infiniband EDR network. The HPC system has a computing power (theoretical peak performance) of 1,202 TFlops. An IBM Spectrum LSF software is used as a job scheduler.

The backend data flow is fed by the CMS model outputs of Sect.2.1.b. Then, twice a day, VISIR-2 optimal routes are computed. After VISIR-2 outputs its results, a post-processing programme is run, to prepare graphical elements (maps, s. Sect.2.1.d) for the subsequent processing steps at frontend level (Sect.2.2.b).

Three ferry engine load values are used: $\chi = 70, 85, \text{ or } 100\%$ of the engine shaft power. 39 departures every three hours are computed. This way, about five full days are covered since the time of the latest analysis of sea currents (more details in [10]). Each of these computations is performed for a total of 30 ordered departure-arrival harbour pairs in the Adriatic-Ionian region. They are listed in Fig.4.b. These computations are performed in parallel, each ordered harbour pair being processed at a distinct node of the HPC facility. In total, every calendar day, more than seven thousand route computations are completed and made publicly available.

2.2 (b) Frontend

The frontend component is the operational chain routinely executed at the CMCC HPC facility to transform the graphical elements from the backend into files used for interactive mapping. The frontend also includes a web application, to consume and visualise both this data and those numerical outputs (route waypoints and route metrics) coming directly from VISIR-2. The web app adopts a responsive layout but, given the large number of details and interacting options, its use on either a desktop computer or a tablet is recommended. More technical features about the frontend can be found in [10].

3. RESULTS

This section presents some results from the GUTTA-VISIR service. It first provides a case study (Sect.3.1) and then an assessment of the first eleven months of operation (Sect.3.2).

3.1 CASE STUDY

¹² <https://www.cmcc.it/super-computing-center-scc>

An example of how the GUTTA-VISIR web app looks like is shown in Fig.3. It is structured into a header menu, a sidebar, a body, and a footer. The header menu contains, on the right-hand side, links to other pages of the application (Home, About, Help, Feedback, News). The left sidebar contains the logo of the GUTTA project, along with several options which need to be selected or modified by the user to visualise, in the web app’s body, the desired results. It also contains the information about the time, both the wave and current forecasts were issued. The footer contains the logos of the GUTTA project partners and the funding information.

Figure 3: GUTTA-VISIR web app, upon selection of WEST in Route and click on a specific element of the Brindisi-Patras route bundle. The thickest route (Zadar-Barletta) shown in the map corresponds to the largest marker in the left scatter plot with CII vs. CO₂ savings and to the CO₂ emission profiles in the bottom right corner.

The sidebar includes tools to select both the route and its departure date and time, as well as the ferry engine load factor and some visualisation and export options. These selections affect what is displayed in the body. However, users may interact with the web app directly from the body, by selecting the end ports of the route from the map. It is possible to choose among 30 oriented routes, corresponding to either East- or Westbound sailing between 15 couples of harbours. Either individual optimal routes (like what shown in Fig.1) or bundles of routes with varying departure time and engine load (as in Fig.3) can be shown.

The routes can be explored not only in their geographical aspects, but also through some key metrics relevant to decarbonisation. They are reported in the upper part of the body (right below the web app’s header menu) and include route length and duration, total CO₂ emissions, and several carbon intensity indicators (CII). The latter two metrics will be the topic of a systematic assessment done in the subsequent section (Sect.3.2.b.)

The body of the GUTTA-VISIR web app includes a section with a scatter plot of CII vs. CO₂ savings. In VISIR, both CII and CO₂ relative savings are computed with respect to the least-distance route. In the scatter plot, they are displayed for all routes between given harbours but different departure times and engine load. In [8] it is proven that the difference between these two metrics is related to the lengthening of the route due to the numerical optimization process. Thus, this plot conveys synthetic information on how effective diversions are in reducing carbon footprint of routes.

The body also includes a section (“linechart”) with information along a specific route, useful to compare either the CO₂ or the CII timeline of the CO₂-optimal vs. the fastest and the shortest route between the same ports.

Finally, the CO₂-optimal routes selected for display can also be downloaded in either XML or JSON format. A massive download capacity is also available, through the CMCC data delivery system¹³. It offers an API for batch download of all routes published by GUTTA-VISIR since November 2021. They can be filtered by harbour, engine load, and date.

¹³ <https://dds.cmcc.it/#/dataset/gutta-visir/routes>

A structured support information for the end user is provided along with GUTTA-VISIR, in both the About and Help sections of the application. A video tutorial of the service is also available¹⁴. Users feedback can be collected from a specific section of the application¹⁵, and it was assessed in [12]. The Copernicus Marine Service has, since June 2022, listed GUTTA-VISIR as a use case¹⁶.

3.2 SYSTEMATIC ASSESSMENT

In [8] some initial results of the VISIR-2 model in the Adriatic Sea were presented, making the point that systematic investigations on different routes and dates would be possible once an operational tool is realized. In the meantime, the GUTTA-VISIR entered operations, and has been operating for one year now. Questions like: “What CO₂ emission savings are achievable for ferries in the Adriatic Sea?”, “How do they depend on the actual marine conditions or the geographic location of the routes?”, “What CII savings are obtained and what fraction of the mandated ones do they represent?” can now be addressed.

To this end, all optimal routes so far produced by the operational system were analysed. This means covering the November 2021 - September 2022 time frame. The GUTTA-VISIR system has been operational since the beginning of October 2021, but the first month’s data had to be pruned due to a bug in production. This led to a total of 330 days, which were analysed for the present work. On each of these days, data for all the 30 (=15*2) oriented routes were collected, and just routes with departure times at 0:00, 3:00, 6:00, and 9:00 UTC from each port were considered. This was done for keeping in the dataset just voyages reaching destination within the same calendar day of their start. This constraint was applied in view of the subsequent analysis of Sect.3.2.b., where the CO₂ savings will be related to daily-average sea conditions. However, in GUTTA-VISIR there is no limitation regarding routes extending over multiple days.

The CO₂ savings were averaged over the considered departure times, resulting in a dataset of N₁ = 9,900 (=330*15*2) entries. Each of them was augmented with information about the average sea conditions. This was computed from daily averages of CMS analysis fields (Sect.2.1.b) for the specific date. They were spatially averaged in the subregion the route belonged to. The association between routes and subregions is provided in Fig.4.b.

Figure 4: a) The four subregions (North-Centre-South-Ionian) of the Adriatic-Ionian region considered in this work. The considered harbours are marked by grey circles and labelled with their international seaport codes. b) Association of the 15 GUTTA-VISIR routes (just Eastbound ones listed) to the subregions of a).

For this work, we restricted the analysis to the GUTTA-VISIR routes relative to an engine load factor $\chi = 70\%$. The CO₂ savings were assessed in relation to both date of navigation and marine conditions (Sect.3.2.a) and sea domain (Sect.3.2.b).

3.2 (a) Role of marine conditions

The timeseries of the CO₂ savings for all routes of the region of interest are displayed in Fig.5.

¹⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-qORsU-Jh_8

¹⁵ <https://www.gutta-visir.eu/other/feedback>

¹⁶ <https://marine.copernicus.eu/services/use-cases/gutta-visir-decision-support-system-ferries-adriatic-sea>

Figure 5: Time series of the CO₂ savings with marker colour representing a) significant wave height; b) current magnitude. Dataset with N₁ = 9,900 entries used.

The largest savings are seen in the December-May period and can even exceed 20%. The summer values are on the average smaller, but there are two dates with savings exceeding 10%. The significant wave height always exceeded three metres whenever the savings were larger than 20%. However, during those events, the magnitude of the sea surface current could be any.

To investigate more directly the role of both waves and currents, they are used as independent variables in Fig.6's panels.

Figure 6: CO₂ savings as functions of a) significant wave height; b) current magnitude, with related date coded in the marker colour. Dataset with N₁ = 9,900 entries used.

It is seen that the CO₂ savings increase their variability as the significant wave height $\langle H_s \rangle$, averaged in the related subregion, increases. No similar effect is seen in relation to the current magnitude $\langle w \rangle$. From Fig.6.a, the maximum CO₂ savings can be related to the sea state through the approximate relationship:

$$\max\{-\Delta CO_2 [\%]\} \approx 6 \langle H_s [m] \rangle \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

However, it should be stressed that the actual CO₂ savings can be any positive value smaller than what predicted by Eq.1

3.2 (b) Role of sea domain

The Adriatic-Ionian region includes both the Adriatic Sea, a marginal sea of the Mediterranean Sea with a Northwest to Southeast elongation, and the Northern Ionian Sea, a geographic sector we here defined to cover the marine domain between the Otranto Strait and the Patras Gulf.

The sea state in the Adriatic-Ionian region is characterised by a strong spatial inhomogeneity. Both the typical and extreme wind-waves are larger in the southern part of the domain. The median value of the typical waves ranges from 0.25 to 1.5 m in summer and from 0.5 to 3 m in winter, with a clear Northwest-Southeast gradient [2]. The circulation in the Adriatic is characterised by intense current segments in its western side, and three cyclonic gyres corresponding to the subregions

called “North”, “Centre”, and “South” in this paper. In autumn, there is a prevalent cyclonic circulation in the whole basin, with intensification of the three gyres [1].

For investigating geographic peculiarities in the GUTTA-VISIR data, the routes were first disaggregated on the departure times. Hence the corresponding dataset includes $N_2 = 19,800$ ($=330 \cdot 15 \cdot 4$) routes for each orientation (East- or Westbound). The dataset was then decomposed into the four subregions.

The largest CO₂ savings for Eastbound and Westbound routes were found in the “North” (30.4%) and in the “Ionian” (28.8%) subregions of Fig.4.a respectively. However, it is important to realise that the savings have a specific statistical distribution, as displayed in Fig.7.

Figure 7: Statistical distributions of CO₂ savings for a) west- and b) eastbound routes. The colours refer to the subregions in Fig.4a. Markers are the values of histograms with a bin size of 0.05%. The solid lines are least-square fits of exponential functions as in Eq.2 with the C parameter as in legend. Dataset with $N_2 = 19,800$ entries for each sailing direction (East- or Westbound) used.

There, we compared the histogram data to fits of a mono-exponential function

$$p(x) = A * \exp(-x/C) \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

Where the quantity C also is the expectation value of the distribution. Routes from most subregions are exponentially distributed over three orders of magnitude. Largest deviations are seen for Eastbound (Westbound) routes of the “North” (“Ionian”) subregion. In the former case, CO₂ savings larger than 0.6% are more likely than in an exponential curve. In the latter, savings smaller than 0.3% are less likely than in the exponential. This is reflected in the comparisons of the sample mean to the C fit parameter in Tab.2. These statistical deviations could be due to wave climate peculiarities (the “North” subregion is affected by the Bora wind; the “Ionian” routes imply sailing through the Otranto Strait, which is hardly calm) and possibly also by an inadequate spatial sampling (in our study, “North” and “Ionian” are the subregions with the least routes, cf. Fig.4b).

Table 2: Average CO₂ savings (in %), distinguished by subregions and prevalent direction of sailing. Both the fit function’s (Eq.2) and the sample mean are provided.

	Eastbound		Westbound	
	C	sample	C	sample
North	0.23	0.69	0.20	0.23
Centre	0.65	1.00	0.57	0.68
South	1.26	1.28	0.23	0.69
Ionian	1.20	1.36	1.05	1.53

The values from Tab.2 are clearly lower than those predicted by Eq.1 using the average sea state values mentioned at the beginning of this subsection. Indeed, the former are mean while the latter are maximum values. The absolute CO₂ savings of the GUTTA-VISIR optimal routes are provided in Tab.3. This information reflects both the relative savings in Tab.2 and the number of routes in each subregion, cf. Fig.4b. It is seen that a total of about 1.0 kt CO₂ would have been saved in just the Adriatic-Ionian region, during the reference period of this study of about eleven months. Considering that the total emissions along least-distance routes would have been 92.9 kt CO₂ the average savings are about 1.1%.

Table 3: Absolute CO₂ savings (in tonnes) for the eleven months of operation, distinguishing subregions, and direction of sailing. The dataset with N₁ entries per direction of sailing was used in input.

	Eastbound	Westbound
North	59.6	17.6
Centre	191.3	126.1
South	205.6	121.4
Ionian	139.3	163.3
subtotals	595.9	428.4
total	1,024.2	

The cost of bunker fuel, considering both the market value¹⁷ and the allowances to be purchased in case of inclusion of shipping into the EU-ETS (Sect.1), can easily exceed 1 kEUR/tonne. If low carbon fuels are used, the cost could easily double¹⁸. Thus, the CO₂ relative savings in Tab.3 can have an economic value of the order of one million Euro per year. It should be recalled that they refer to just a small portion of the global ocean (the Adriatic-Ionian region), and just consider one vessel type (ferries).

Finally, we assessed the CII savings computed by GUTTA-VISIR during the first eleven months of operation. As shown in [8], CII savings are given by the sum of the CO₂ savings and the optimal route's relative lengthening with respect to the geodetic one. In view of the IMO regulation on CII mentioned in Sect.1, it would be interesting to assess if it could be fulfilled via the CII savings of optimal routes, and to what extent. To this end, we computed the distribution of CII savings exceeding a given value. They are provided in Fig.8, for the datasets of 2N₂ routes.

Figure 8: Statistical distributions of minimum CII savings for a) west- and b) eastbound routes. The vertical dashed lines refer to the target CII savings mandated by IMO by the years printed in the labels, taking 2019 as a baseline.

¹⁷ <https://shipandbunker.com/prices>

¹⁸ https://www.globalmaritimeforum.org/content/2022/03/Insight-brief_Methanol-as-a-scalable-zero-emission-fuel.pdf

From Fig.8 it is seen that most of the optimal routes have small CII savings, but quite large CII savings are also possible. If the Eastbound routes are considered, the four subregions have a similar distribution. For the Westbound ones instead, the fraction of “Ionian” routes with minimum CII savings up to about 30% is clearly larger than in the rest of the Adriatic-Ionian region. In Fig.8 the CII reduction targets mandated by IMO till 2026 are also displayed. For Eastbound routes, the GUTTA-VISIR savings represent between 4.7 and 7.5% of the 2023’s target, and they decrease to 1.6-2.5% of the 2026’s target, depending on the subregion. For Westbound routes, they represent more than 11% of 2023’s target for “Ionian” routes, and this decreases to about 5% in 2026.

4. CONCLUSIONS

An operational service for computing and automatically publishing CO₂-optimal ferry routes in the Adriatic-Ionian region based on the VISIR ship routing model has been built. Such GUTTA-VISIR service has now been in continuous operation for about one year, providing open access to thousands of optimal routes, corresponding to various ports of call and departure times, daily.

This technological achievement covers a literature gap about a systematic assessment of the potential impact of ship routing on decarbonisation. By analysing 39,600 routes produced in the time between November 2021 and September 2022, we characterised the relative CO₂ savings of the optimal routes with respect to the emissions along the traditional, least-distance route. The maximum CO₂ savings on a route between given harbours are proportional to the average sea state, and we were able to derive an approximate numerical relationship between them, Eq.1. However, average savings can be much smaller and were investigated via the distribution of CO₂ savings. It was found that the largest mean savings were obtained for routes sailing in the southern part of the basin, where the typical sea states are rougher. The distribution of the savings follows quite closely an exponential one. Statistical deviations are found for specific subregions and could be due to peculiarities of the wave climate or insufficient statistical sampling. The total amount of CO₂ which would have been saved through the GUTTA-VISIR system for just ferries sailing in the Adriatic-Ionian region during the eleven-month period is about one thousand tonne CO₂.

The GUTTA-VISIR service also computed the CII savings of the CO₂-optimal routes. This metric matters in view of the IMO regulation approved at the MEPC-76 meeting. Our data show that a not negligible (up to about one tenth) fraction of the CII reduction target for 2023 could be achieved just by optimal routing. There is a sub-regional specificity in this finding, and the prevailing direction of sailing is found to matter. However, the study indicates that, even for short-sea shipping, route optimization may contribute in a sizable manner to short-term decarbonisation targets. The fraction of decarbonisation provided by routing decreases from more than 10 to about 2% of the IMO-mandated target as, in the coming years, the decarbonisation ambition rises.

To overcome some of the limitations that emerged in this research, it would be interesting to extend this work to a multi-year statistic and to a more spatially dense network of routes. The role of sea currents and engine power could be highlighted by dedicated numerical experiments. Based e.g. on [9], it is expected that ocean-going vessels would benefit even more from optimal routing. Deploying the VISIR model to other regions of the global ocean and making use of realistic representations of other vessel types would offer an objective basis for verifying and quantifying this expectation.

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6. REFERENCES

1. ARTEGIANI, A., BREGANT, D., et al., The Adriatic Sea general circulation. part ii: baroclinic circulation structure, *Journal of physical Oceanography*, 1997.
2. BARBARIOL, F., DAVISON, S., et al., ‘Wind waves in the Mediterranean sea: An ERA5 reanalysis wind-based climatology’, *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 2021.
3. ‘Network Optimization: Continuous and Discrete Models’. *Athena Scientific*, 1998.
4. ‘A note on two problems in connexion with graphs’, *Numerische mathematik*, 1959.
5. FRIEDLINGSTEIN, P., JOHNES M.W., et al., ‘Global Carbon Budget 2021’, *Earth System Science Data*, 2022, doi.org/10.5194/essd-14-1917-2022
6. MEPC.304(72) Initial IMO strategy on reduction of GHG emissions from ships. Technical Report Annex 11, International Maritime Organization, London, UK, 2018.
7. ISWG-GHG 13/3/1 Further consideration of concrete proposals on the revision of the initial strategy, and initiation of the development of a revised strategy, International Maritime Organization, London, UK, 2022.
8. MANNARINI, G., CARELLI, L. et al., ‘Towards Least-CO2 Ferry Routes in the Adriatic Sea’, *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 2021., doi.org/10.3390/jmse9020115

9. MANNARINI, G. and CARELLI, L. VISIR-1.b: Ocean surface gravity waves and currents for energy-efficient navigation. *Geosci. Model Dev.* doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-3449-2019
10. MANNARINI, G., CARELLI, L., et al., ‘Operational prototype of the DSS for Eco-routes’, *Deliverable 4.4.1. of the Italy-Croatia Interreg project GUTTA*, 2022. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6974252
11. MANNARINI, G., SALINAS M. L., et al.,. How COVID-19 Affected GHG Emissions of Ferries in Europe. *Sustainability*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095287>
12. MIHALIĆ, M., OROVIĆ, J., et al., ‘Report on GUTTA eco-routes tool user experience’, *Deliverable 5.1.1. of the Italy-Croatia Interreg project GUTTA*, 2022. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6974258
13. OROVIĆ, J., MANNARINI, G., et al., ‘Report on parametrization of vessel CO2 emissions in terms of environmental state variables’, *Deliverable 4.1.1. of the Italy-Croatia Interreg project GUTTA*, 2021 doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4778523

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